

Urban Arboretum

Marcus A. Gordon
@magfoto (Endemics Collective)
magfoto@me.com

Sarah Imrisek
@cymatiste (Endemics Collective)
sarahimrisek@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research article describes an interactive art installation titled “*Urban Arboretum*” and the work behind its creation. The article discusses *o-sigv*, an instrument for transmodal live coding based on the esoteric language Orca, used to live code a series of biomes. The article also discusses plant growth algorithms created and visualized in the live coding environment Hydra. Combined, the authors and their respective live coding languages were used to deliver both a live coding performance and interactive installation with the voices and sounds of their audience.

1 Introduction

As artists working with code, we view this project as the beginning of exploring the expressivity of code through connections made with nature (or the environment). Since taking this path towards live coding as an art-research practice, today we reflect on the origins of this path, and what Alexandra Cardenas’ writing sparked in us with her 2019 ICLC article “*Street Code*” (Cárdenas 2019). What we soon rediscovered was the connection we had with her narrative about urban spaces and subversion. In reference to the concept of rhythm and its many interpretations, from Henri Lefebvre writings on rhythmanalysis (Lefebvre, Moore, and Elden 2013) as urban exploration, to Geoffrey Toussaints’ mathematical models on the geometry of rhythm (Toussaint 2010), live coding explores these concepts through the performative act. The live coding of music can be seen as generative music with human and non-human interactions that subvert initial machinic intentions of a generative system. This intersection of rhythm and the subversion of machinic automata presents an opportunity for use in architectonic intervention, where computational arts and architecture can intersect in the making of social spaces of action. We see this as our way of building desired futures, placing live coding as our performative act of their social construction.

2 Background

Nuit Blanche Toronto is an all-night twelve-hour art festival that happens in the city every Fall. In 2023, we launched *Urban Arboretum*, an interactive art installation that explored the festivals’ theme of “breaking ground” with outdoor projected animations of plant life. The animations were initiated by, and sometimes simply affected by, participants’ voices and sounds picked up by the installations’ microphone (see Figure 3). To lower the barrier for participation, we placed a small table next to the microphone containing a hand drum, maracas and a bell.

Our project spoke to the idea of resilience and growth, pushing boundaries and exploring new possibilities. Having invited visitors to contribute to the installation through their own voices, the project highlighted the importance of community involvement and collaboration in the creative process. We were *breaking* new ground both in terms of the innovative use of code to create the animations, and in the way that the installation brought together art, technology, and community engagement.

We were also inspired by the growth of the live coding scene in Tkaronto¹, of which we and our ensemble The Endemics are on the vanguard; working to raise the profile of this creative, improvisational art form.

Our unique aesthetic blended organic and geometric elements. Patterns of lines and shapes resembling trees, ferns, flowers and vines stretched up from the concrete. The algorithms allowed for a high degree of complexity and variation, resulting in pieces that were both precise and unpredictable. The overall effect was a mesmerizing, otherworldly beauty that centered the natural world and its resilience as we plunge headfirst into an increasingly technological future.

¹Tkaronto is a Mohawk word meaning “where there are trees standing in the water,” and is considered the original name of Toronto; therefore we use it here as well as in our projection, to honour the city’s Indigenous history and to help decolonize the name.

The canvas for our presentation was the façade of the 401 Richmond Building, a heritage-designated industrial building turned arts and culture hub. Several other Nuit Blanche activations were hosted inside the building, providing a steady stream of visitors throughout the all-night festival.

3 Systems

We describe the live coding languages used and systems made to execute the salient features of the installation and performance.

3.1 sigv

Presented in the Vision Research Conference in 2022 at York University, sigv was presented as a custom tool and mini-language for live coding (Gordon 2022). Inspiration for sigv was derived from a desire To make a tool for live audiovisual performance and composition, and for creative coding applications in art-science (a.k.a. sci-art, ArtScience (Hosale et al. 2021), experimental arts) research.

sigv began as a network of open patches running in the Max environment, to now a standalone desktop application. The application is supported by a host of Bash scripts, and operates on receiving commands primarily via the Open Sound Control (OSC) protocol. Written in a terminal window, the sigv Bash commands either trigger operations in the standalone app, or run as a separate shell/terminal process. These commands that makeup the core of the mini-language, a very simplified version, that are meant to extend to the live coder, a framework for live coding various events, applications, small programs, and batch operations, and many other things that would be normally accessible via the terminal of a laptop they are live coding on.

3.2 Orca

The first attraction to Orca was to its interface and visual syntax. In addition to this, it had a minimal design to it that was a refreshing outlook to typical GUI environments and conventional IDE window arrangements. Another attraction that we have towards Orca was its Rube Goldberg style approach, working with the concept of “bangs” similar to popular visual languages such as Max and Pure Data.

Using Orca for sequencing sound was our first endeavour with the tool, and as such we sought the opportunity to extend that to the visual domain as well as using the language to sequence physical computing components.

3.3 Hydra

Hydra is a live code-able video synth and coding environment, inspired by analog modular synthesis, that runs directly in the browser. Written in JavaScript, Hydra supports P5.js, which was used here to generate line art resembling trees, vines and flowers, which were then mixed with colourful feedback effects live on the scene, and animated in an audio-reactive manner as described below under *Procedural Plant Life*.

3.4 The Nature Object

The background of the projection was a brick wall of the building façade with a small amount of tree branches and foliage stretching over the view (see Figure 4). With this as the canvas, a series of biomes are, one at a time, loaded into the projected scene, and has it parameters set by live coding them. For the biomes to *sense* the incoming audio, a new object was created to support the analysis. The new sigv object created dubbed “nature” used a biquad filter to analyze incoming audio. An example of the code used to bring this object to scene for use, can be seen in the snippet below:

sigv code for loading and using the *nature* object

```
new nature 0 0 nature # load nature object
nature mode bloom 1 #
nature sense med 1
nature mult 100
```

The steps taken above show an example of how the commands for sigv or entered into the command line.

Figure 1: On the left: Orca with custom theme color showing an example algorithm written on the grid. On the right: A point cloud biome is displayed here while a custom Bash script is being created to set it in motion

Figure 2: o-sigv operators classified in their respective groups

3.5 o-sigv

Writing code with Orca is a pleasant and fun arrangement of characters on a grid. For the exhibition, various rhythm patterns were injected into the grid for use, as well as o-sigv custom operators. o-sigv was created with eight classification groups of operators:

- ANIM // motion based commands
- MAT // material and texture commands
- LIGHTS // lighting commands
- TRANS // transformation commands
- SYSTEM // system-based commands
- SERIAL // physical computing commands
- CHAO // chaos commands (default Lorenz)
- AUDIO // audio interface commands

Taking the nature command as an example, it is placed in the AUDIO group due to its function is based on sound. As shown in the figure, you'll notice the Orca syntax for this group uses the underscore (_) character. Each group uses a special character to address a particular sigv command and parameter. All of these o-sigv commands are based on OSC, therefore are custom replicas of Orca's OSC operator (=). In sigv, as a command-line focused mini-language, the help files for the commands are written as Linux-based man pages. In this same spirit, o-sigv help files are written in plain text, and also accessed and viewed via the command-line (see Figure 4).

Figure 3: Setup of Urban Arboretum exhibition

4 Live Coding *en plein air*

We decided that the experience of live coding for this project, would best be experienced with us situated outside, live coding with the elements. Instead we opted for a setup that just ensured that participants were outdoors, under an umbrella, capable of interacting with the microphone, and able to see the wall with the projection. Having placed ourselves however, at the windows, worked well for giving us access to still sometimes hear our participants directly without speakers, allowing us to monitor and change audio capture sensitivity in sigv.

4.1 Procedural Plant Life

The procedural plants were coded in P5.js through hydra and consisted of three elements:

- A wavy tree made with L-systems of curves
- Vines resembling sine waves with elliptical leaves on each side of the vines, each one being generated with random variation in waviness and the shape of the leaves
- Star-shaped flowers.

Each of these was coded to respond to a different type of audio signal, to reward experimentation with different kinds of sounds. These audio cues were differentiated by which section of Hydra's 4-band FFT audio response was activated and by how long it was activated:

The maracas and bell activated higher band responses and these triggered star-flowers to appear one at a time and then slowly drop and fade, such that extended shaking of the maracas led to a cascade of star-flowers that appeared randomly throughout the scene and rose up while the sound was being played, only to fall down and disappear in the ensuing silence.

The drums, and speech, activated lower band responses and these caused vines to appear and to stretch upward from the bottom of the wall.

The tree shape only appeared in response to sustained audio activation, as a special reward to engaged participants; it grew from a small shape at the bottom of the wall to a large shape covering a significant portion of the wall, and responded to active fluctuations in volume by animating the L-system rotation to open and close the branches with colourful trails, staying still and slowly shrinking during periods of quiet. Singing was particularly good at activating the tree. The design for the

Figure 4: Sample procedural plant life

Figure 5: Sample biomes

tree was based on the example at <https://p5js.org/examples/simulate-recursive-tree.html>, a variant of Daniel Shiffman's Recursive Tree for Processing, and modified to use curves instead of lines (Shiffman n.d.).

While secondary aspects of the animation of these elements responded directly to fluctuations in volume, two extra audio functions were written to smooth out the audio response by creating copies of the FFT band data, which were slowly incremented and decremented to provide a short-term and long-term average of recent audio activity:

```
slowA = [0,0,0,0];
sensitivity = [0.25,0.3,0.3,0.3];
slowgrow = (band)=>{
  if(a.fft[band]>sensitivity[band]){
    slowA[band] = Math.min(1,slowA[band]+0.005);
  } else {
    slowA[band] = Math.max(0,slowA[band]-0.003);
  }
}
```

These averages were used to allow slower animation of the vines and trees growing, and to facilitate the plants slowly shrinking after the sound stopped, instead of swiftly disappearing.

4.2 A Network of Biomes

Environmental art scenes of a speculative Tkaronto viewed as green landscapes and cityscapes, focused on its trees, vegetation and plant life and the biodiversity driven by the city's many ravines. Represented as a series of projected urban biomes, the environment grounds sometimes have beautiful green grass, wild weeds, and flourishing shrubs.

Tkaronto is a growing city, sensitized by its many microclimates, another unique characteristic of the city's biodiversity. The speculative design of the biomes in this projection installation, are imaginary environmental structures of a city in ruin, a city filled with various energies, a city experiencing renewal, reconciliation, change, joy, hope, and sorrow. . . .all at once.

The biomes were made using the open-source 3D application Blender with various plugins and libraries for vegetation assets.

5 Conclusion

We set out to use code as a medium to facilitate symbolic interactions between urban inhabitants and the natural environment, and we were delighted with the community's reception. Over 10,000 visitors engaged with our installation, some

spontaneously breaking into song or rap and performing complex rhythms at the microphones. Many conversations were sparked about the underlying themes, and many people were curious about the technological underpinnings of the performance.

While much of the overall functionality was pre-coded before the event, we took advantage of our live coding environments to modify the responsiveness of our projections in real time throughout the event. We feel that this improvisational element enabled us to craft an experience that was more in tune with the movements of the audience, adding in extra flourishes at times of significant engagement, and selecting and switching between biomes to cater to the changing mood and energy of the crowd throughout the night. Providing instruments was a last minute decision that worked very well to encourage shy participants to engage with the audio-reactivity. Overall, the blurry line between performance and installation added a level of intrigue that accentuated the magical nature of the experience for the audience.

We would like to develop further iterations of this performance, applying our projection mapping to other locations and creating further unique designs tailored to their specific architecture and history.

This format has great potential to be scaled and modified for diverse applications, and we are excited to continue to explore the potential for live coding in interactive art installations. We demonstrated the potential of interactive art to not only mirror the complexity of human interaction with our environments, but to enrich it, inviting participants to become co-creators of meaning and experience. The fusion of technology with improvisation opens up a world where art is not static but a living ecosystem, responsive and ever-changing, reflecting the fluidity of human creativity. We are proud to participate in this shift towards a more inclusive, participatory, and dynamic art form.

5.1 Acknowledgments

A thank you to the architectural space that hosted this installation, 401 Richmond Street West, curator William Huffman, and the organizers of Nuit Blanche TO 2023.

References

- 10 Cárdenas, Alexandra. 2019. "Street Code - Live Coding in Public Space." In *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Live Coding*, 353. Madrid, Spain: Medialab Prado / Madrid Destino. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946288>.
- Gordon, Marcus. 2022. "Sigv: A Mini-Language for Transmodal Live Coding." ResearchGate. <http://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28943.66729>.
- Hosale, Mark-David, James Madsen, Robert Allison, and Marcus Gordon. 2021. "ArtScience and the ICECUBE LED Display [ILDm³]." In Chengdu, China: ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3474085.3475524>.
- Lefebvre, H., G. Moore, and S. Elden. 2013. *Rhythmanalysis: Space, Time and Everyday Life*. Bloomsbury Revelations. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Shiffman, Daniel. n.d. "Recursive Tree for Processing | P5.js Examples." Accessed February 15, 2024. <https://p5js.org/examples/simulate-recursive-tree.html>.
- Toussaint, Godfried. 2010. "Computational Geometric Aspects of Rhythm, Melody, and Voice-Leading." *Computational Geometry* 43 (1): 2–22.